

ACCELERATING CLUE WITH INTEL ONEAPI SYCL

August 2022

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

Heterogeneous Computing is becoming more and more popular due to the advent of new computing resources such as Graphics Processing Units (GPUs) and Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGAs) and can be exploited in computing farms to achieve a better time, cost, and energy to the solution. In principle to run on different architectures, multiple implementations of the same algorithm are needed, making the code hard to maintain, test, and validate. Performance Portability frameworks, like Intel OneAPI, allow writing a single source code that can run on different architectures. This project aims to use Intel OneAPI, to accelerate the CLUE Algorithm reconstruction in a single source code that can be executed with good performance on multiple platforms like CPU, GPUs, and FPGAs, while also designing user-friendly interfaces for common tasks such as memory operations, work division optimization and kernel launches, always looking for high performance.

ABSTRACT

Parallel particle reconstruction algorithms are necessary to sustain the increasing event output size and frequency of high granularity calorimeters (HGCal) like the ones installed in the LHC at CERN. Employing hardware accelerators like GPUs or FPGAs and their respective SDKs has resulted in parallel applications capable of handling the required throughput demand. However, it brings a new software development challenge when a combination of different vendors and architecture hardware accelerators are used to run the programs. Performance portability frameworks like OpenCL, Alpaka, among others have been recently developed to enable heterogeneous applications to run on multiple hardware. Selecting any of them requires exploring the benefits and drawbacks of each technology to make an informed decision. In this work, the performance portability framework SYCL with DPC++ was used to re-implement the energy clustering algorithm (CLUE) with the purpose to evaluate the potential benefits of the framework, efficiency in contrast to native implementations and generate a SYCL porting knowledge base useful for future projects.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Context

The output data produced by High Granularity Calorimeters like the one installed in CMS is not usable for physical analysis in its raw form. This is because raw detector data is a collection of sensor cell activations and hardware signals that have to be processed by particle reconstruction algorithms to obtain the meaningful physical objects in each collision event. One of the algorithms developed at CMS and employed during the reconstruction pipeline is "CLUE" [3], a density-based clustering algorithm used to identify the individual created particles by clustering nearby energy deposits. It is different from other clustering algorithms like "DBSCAN" [1] as it was designed to be highly parallelizable to process the huge event input data and scale the throughput capacity with additional hardware resources. CLUE was originally implemented in C++/CUDA and achieved low input processing time of few milliseconds per event when running on NVIDIA GPU's.

1.2 Heterogeneous Computing Applications

The combination of different hardware accelerator (HA) architectures like FPGAs or GPUs as well as different vendors like NVIDIA, AMD and Intel introduce a software development challenge on performance-critical applications. Programming multiple implementations for each HA type would lead to a big proportion of code duplication which translates into a significant cost on software development, as there is more code to maintain, it is prone to errors and requires a large amount of expertise (for each HA type and SDK). As a response to this problem, performance portability frameworks and programming models have been created in recent years like OpenCL [4], Alpaka [7], SYCL [5], etc. These technologies connect to the underlying HA and provide an abstraction layer on top so that applications can be programmed to run on any hardware resource. Choosing between any of them requires exploration to get to know the benefits and drawbacks. In CMS, Alpaka has been already tested, but new open standards like SYCL have received a lot of attention lately. SYCL looks promising as it's backed by big organizations like Intel and is defined as a library on top of modern C++.

1.3 Objective

The aim of this project is to evaluate the efficiency of Intel's oneAPI SYCL while porting CLUE into heterogeneous computing. The resulting application should be able to run on multiple HA types, avoid code duplication, produce always correct results and have similar computing performance. Furthermore, it is desirable to know if the application event processing throughput scales with the use of multiple concurrent HA devices.

This work's contributions are:

- An open-sourced heterogeneous version of CLUE written in C++/SYCL capable on running multiple hardware accelerator types (NVIDIA's GPUs, Intel GPUs, CPUs and FPGA emulators)
- Performance evaluation insights between SYCL and native implementations on both GPU and CPU devices.
- A knowledge base of porting patterns, resources, tips and pitfalls when developing/porting applications with SYCL.

2 Required Concepts

2.1 Event Processing

The objective of the particle reconstruction pipeline is to process the raw data coming from a series of collision events to recreate the physical objects produced in such events. A particle reconstruction algorithm takes as input the data for a single collision **event** and produces meaningful physical objects. The time it takes an algorithm to process an event is referred as **latency**. An algorithm is run multiple times to process many events from the series, the amount of events that can be processed in a unit of time is called the **throughput**. To increase the throughput, the algorithm can be **speedup** to process a single event on a shorter amount of time. Another option is to distribute the event jobs among multiple concurrent workers. Each worker is an execution of the algorithm and runs on an independent HA **stream**; this technique is referred as **streaming**.

2.2 CLUE

CLUE is a density based clustering algorithm which means it performs best when the points to be clustered resemble Gaussian distributions. This fits perfectly the detector data for which is meant to be used: particle fragmented energy deposits. Furthermore, it provides the essential assumptions from which the algorithm key ideas are developed and can be trivially expressed as parallel problems.

CLUE works by first computing spatial-relationship properties to each point such as *density* and *distance-to-nearest-point-with-higher-density* and then, identifying the points with outlier properties to classify them as cluster center seeds or noise. The whole algorithm is structured into 5 steps as shown in Fig. 1. Each step can be massively parallelized in a *Single Instruction Multiple Data* (SIMD) way. Therefore, the CUDA code of CLUE first, allocates device memory to hold the input points and required data structures by the algorithm; then, it copies from host the input points and executes in order the 5 steps as device kernels; finally, it copies back the points with the assigned cluster index and frees device memory resources. Due to its SIMD nature, little thread synchronization has to be made with the only exception of ensuring thread-safe *push()* and *pop()* operations on a stack data structure.

Figure 1: CLUE's flow diagram of main steps that can be programmed as device kernels.

2.3 SYCL

SYCL is a cross-platform abstraction that enables developers to make heterogeneous computing applications on plain modern C++ in a similar fashion like other parallel programming models like OpenCL [5]. It does it by allowing code to be compiled to device code according to the targeted hardware architectures and be run seamlessly to the programmer. For that end, it defines several models for execution, memory and programming that SYCL implementations must provide.

2.3.1 Execution Model

A SYCL application is composed of 1) device code that will be executed on different hardware accelerators according to the device; and 2), host code that is responsible of setting up the application, loading the data, managing the hardware resources and submitting code kernels to be executed by devices.

The controlling object for doing memory, synchronization and kernel launching operations on devices is the *queue*. By creating an instance of a queue to an individual device, one can perform multiple types of operations on that device. Listing 1 shows an example of a simple SYCL application that will increment in parallel a vector of numbers. For more SYCL learning resources, one can check the official specification [5] or the SYCL Academy free learning materials [2] for great explanations on programming with SYCL, examples and exercises.

```
#include <CL/sycl.h>
#include <vector>
#define N 512

// Kernel function that is going to be executed on the accelerator device
void vectorIncrement(int a*, int idx) {
    a[idx] += 1;
}

int main() {
    std::vector a(N, 0);
    // Creating the sycl::queue object to submit work to
    // an accelerator device in the system
    sycl::queue queue(sycl::default_selector());
    // Get a block of memory from the device to store the data to be processed
    int d_a* = (int*)sycl::malloc_device(N*sizeof(int), queue);
    // Copy the data from host computer to device memory
    queue.memcpy(d_a, a.data(), N*sizeof(int));

    // Submit work to the device with parallel_for to execute multiple instances
    // of the vectorIncrement kernel, one for each work item
    queue.submit([&](sycl::handler& cgh){
        cgh.parallel_for(N, [=](int idx){
            vectorIncrement(d_a, idx);
        });
    });
    // Copy the result data back to cpu
    queue.memcpy(a.data(), d_a, N*sizeof(int));
    // Free memory for the device associated to the queue
    sycl::free(d_a, queue);

    return 0;
}
```

Listing 1: Example of a simple SYCL application

2.3.2 Backend and Implementations

To be able to operate on a device and use functionalities, SYCL backends connects to the targeted device API and provides a bridge to execute the generic SYCL instructions. A SYCL implementation includes multiples backends and puts their devices at the disposal of the programmer according to the device type queried. As Fig 2 shows, there are several SYCL implementations in development by multiple organizations. Each one of them offers different backends, nonetheless, all must allow to compile and run any SYCL compliant application.

Figure 2: SYCL most popular implementations.

3 Solution

The end product of this work is an heterogeneous computing application as depicted in Fig 3 that runs the CLUE algorithm. It is written in C++/SYCL using Intel’s SYCL implementation to produce a runnable application capable of executing on Intel’s CPU’s, GPU’s and FPGA emulators as well as NVIDIA GPU. The final code can be found in its [Github Repository](#) [10]. Furthermore, the application was enhanced, beyond initial project specification, with the integration of a light-weight version of the CMS Software Framework (1w-CMSSW) [CMSSW], which enables event processing streaming on multiple concurrent devices. The scope of the project was extended as the time budget allowed it.

Figure 3: CLUE Solution Stack.

3.1 Selection of Intel oneAPI SYCL

The compiler chosen for the project is the DPC++ compiler that can be obtained from Intel's oneAPI base toolkit [6]. The reasons for choosing Intel's implementation are as follows: first, it is backed by a stable company that can provide long-term development and support; second, it provides close customer support to attend SYCL concerns, questions and issues; finally, Intel has other profiling and debugging tools that integrate well.

3.2 Pixeltrack Device Streaming Framework

For increasing throughput of the application, the CLUE application was integrated into the Pixeltrack Device Streaming Framework [9]. lw-CMSSW Framework is a smaller version of CMSSW in which computing processes are defined as a chain of producers and consumers. These modules are instantiated on streams running over different concurrent HA devices to process multiple events simultaneously. The CLUE algorithm was programmed as a module along with some optional result validation modules. The modules design for the CLUE application using the lw-CMSSW Framework can be found on Fig 9 in Appendix A.

4 Methodology

It is now described the procedure for the application coding, compilation, testing and performance evaluation. Several artifacts of relevance were produced on this process but are excluded from Section 5 on Results as this section is reserved to analyze the end CLUE application.

4.1 Porting Code

For obtaining a SYCL implementation a "replace-by-equivalent" strategy from CUDA code to SYCL code was employed. This worked well because 1) the amount of lines with CUDA code to be replaced was little (less than 500); and 2), the SYCL API is very similar to CUDA, so in most of the cases there was a direct SYCL substitution like for memory operations, kernel reserved variables or atomic operations.

In some occasions, it was necessary to use additional synchronization features. To obtain the right order of execution of kernels, it was necessary to construct a *queue* with the *inorder* property. Also, for assuring memory consistency and avoiding invalid memory access *.wait()* was used to synchronize memory operations and kernel executions.

Some precaution has to be put when developing SYCL applications. For example, like in multi-threaded applications, it is necessary to keep in mind the memory ownership to make sure memory in use is not deallocated by another thread, or in this case, the host device. Another thing to be aware of is that multiple compilers are being used to generate the kernels native code, and so, properly managing a consistent set of parameters will facilitate the debugging activities.

To facilitate the creation of SYCL programs, specially those that already have a previous CUDA implementation, a "CUDA to SYCL" porting guide was written along with a compiler guide with the learnings from the next subsection. The guides can be found in the [Patatrack Wiki Website](#) [8].

4.2 Building Application

A CMake file was created with the necessary commands to build the application. It is only necessary to install the requirements and follow the instructions in the repo's Readme.

4.2.1 Enabling CUDA backend

Compiling SYCL applications for running on Intel hardware is straightforward with DPC++ and Intel Official Documentation. However, to enable support to experimental backends like AMD or NVIDIA, one has to use the open source DPC++ LLVM-based compiler. The process requires building the compiler with support for CUDA backend and installing in the machine the low-level runtimes necessary to compile and run device code. A SYCL compiling guide "Building and Using Intel LLVM Compiler" was also added to the patatrack wiki[8] with all the necessary details to obtain the compiler, compile for different backends and differences to the commercial DPC++ compiler.

4.2.2 Building on machines with different compilers

At the beginning, the commercial DPC++ compiler was the only one used, as it is the official release, it optimized and works best with Intel tools. It was installed on the Virtual Machine "olice-05" that has Intel CPU, GPU and FPGA emulators. However, there was a need to evaluate the application on NVIDIA GPU that could be found on "patatrack02" VM. So each VM got a different compiler installation, commercial DPC++ for "olice-05" and custom built with CUDA support on "patatrack02".

To support one codebase independent of machine where it's being built, the Makefile script is conditionally controlled by an optional environment variable to execute one set of instructions for each compiler.

4.3 Verifying Correctness

To assert that the new SYCL implementation was producing valid results, a testing strategy based on "comparison-against-truth" was followed. The process consists of first, running the original implementation to record the values of the computed properties and results for a given input event. Then, the new SYCL implementation can be ran with the same input event and the values would be again recorded. Finally, these values from different implementations can be compared against each other to see if they are equal, therefore correct.

The resulting *clusterIndex* value for each point depends on the execution order of the threads so the testing process had to be slightly modified. Due to the algorithmic design of CLUE, the order of the threads determines the *clusterIndex* label to each cluster, as they are assigned following a shared global counter. This might alter the label of each cluster, but does not modify the fact that points belonging to the same cluster must all have the same *clusterIndex*. To test the marked points by the SYCL implementation is the same as the original, it is just necessary to find a mapping between the cluster labels and then compare. The algorithm for doing this can be found on Listing 2 in Appendix A.

The verification logic was programmed into a processing module in the final application so that the CLUE application can be optionally tested when the code changes.

4.4 Evaluating Performance

To evaluate the performance of the new implementation two tests are performed. One to corroborate that the SYCL implementation execution times are close to those with the native implementation. The second test is used to determine if the employment of multiple concurrent HA devices via streaming, increases the throughput of the application.

The first experiment executes native and SYCL implementations on the Intel CPU Xeon Gold 6336Y, Intel GPU Artix P and NVIDIA GPU A10. The measured metric is mean latency of processing 1 event on 10 test runs. The second experiment executes only the SYCL implementation on 1, 2 and 3 concurrent NVIDIA GPU (A10, Tesla V100 and Tesla T4). The measured metric is mean event processing throughput after 10 test runs on 100 events. Furthermore, several environmental variables are set to constraint SYCL default CPU behaviour. As SYCL CPU backend operates on oneTBB, it distributes all the work item jobs among all possible threads, which is nothing close to the native serial code. For this reason, variable `DPCPP_CPU_NUM_CUS` was set to `1` and `DPCPP_CPU_CU_AFFINITY` to `close`, so that it executes as a serial single threaded program.

For each experiment, the application was run against the benchmarking input files: {toyDetector1k.csv, toyDetector2k.csv, ..., toyDetector10k.csv}. Each input file contains a different amount of points, for example toyDetector1k contains 1000*100 points and toyDetector2k contains 2000*100 points. The application performance against the input size are plotted and presented in the next section.

Figure 4: toyDetector input files of different sizes

5 Results

Three results are presented on the following subsections. The first one demonstrates the original premise of the task, running CLUE on multiple HA device types. The remaining two are performance evaluations of the SYCL technology.

5.1 Heterogeneous capability of CLUE

The SYCL CLUE application first obtains a list of possible devices that can be used to run the algorithm with multiple or single streaming mode. The list is collected by invoking SYCL `.get_devices()` function, which will only return devices from available backends that were targeted on compilation. The list on Fig 5 shows that the CLUE application was compiled with the support of all these different architectures: Intel CPU, GPU, FPGA and NVIDIA GPU. The application is capable of running on any of these devices if the required shared libraries can be found, for example, CUDA `.so` files in `$PATH`.


```
[jollivera@patatrack01 heterogeneous-clue]$ ./sycl --maxEvents 1
Found 9 SYCL devices:
- Intel(R) FPGA Emulation Device
- Intel(R) Core(TM) i9-9900K CPU @ 3.60GHz
- Intel(R) Core(TM) i9-9900K CPU @ 3.60GHz
- Intel(R) UHD Graphics 630 [0x3e98]
- Intel(R) Core(TM) i9-9900K CPU @ 3.60GHz
- Intel(R) FPGA Emulation Device
- Intel(R) UHD Graphics 630 [0x3e98]
- Tesla K40c
- SYCL host device

Running CLUE algorithm with the following parameters:
```

Figure 5: Running CLUE detects Intel and NVIDIA devices available to use.

The presented screenshot comes from an execution from the application compiled by the DPC++ LLVM compiler with CUDA support and running in "patatrack01". Adding support for AMD GPUs, should be in theory a matter of rebuilding the DPC++ compiler with HIP backend flag enabled. With this new installation of the compiler and the ROCm runtime installed, one could compile the CLUE targeting the HIP backend and run it without any modification needed.

5.2 Performance Analysis of CLUE SYCL vs Native

For conducting a performance portability evaluation, the SYCL application was run against the native implementation to compare the latency of processing 1 event input of various sizes. In Fig 6 the mean latency of the runs is plotted against the input size. Dashed lines represents measurements from CLUE's SYCL implementation while solid lines stand for the native implementation.

From the graph, it is noticeable that CLUE SYCL performance is close to or better than the original native application performance. Specifically, SYCL single threaded CPU execution outperforms significantly the original serial code. This is an unexpected result considering that the execution behaviour of SYCL under CPU's was controlled via environmental variables to closely match single threaded serial execution, however, some additional optimizations are possible being applied under the hood by Intel's SYCL implementation and compiler.

On the other hand, NVIDIA GPU execution time with SYCL is only slightly higher to the native application, which is what it was anticipated and hoped. In contrast to serial code, it is confirmed that SYCL GPU execution represents a speedup equivalent to using CUDA. Also Intel GPU is able to provide a significant speedup closes to the NVIDIA GPU.

A closer inspection on GPU execution can be seen in Fig 7. The largest performance gap between SYCL and native implementation is of 20ms for the largest input size (10k points). The SYCL framework overhead appears to be constant as the latency time growth rate is very similar to the native growth rate, making SYCL a promising portability framework. We can also see that the Intel GPU, although close to the NVIDIA GPU, grows quicker for larger inputs.

Latency of Processing 1 Event - Native vs SYCL

Figure 6: Performance comparison between CLUE’s native implementation vs SYCL shows close or better performance than native

Latency of Processing 1 Event - Native vs SYCL

Figure 7: Closer look at performance comparison between native vs SYCL on GPU devices

5.3 Performance Analysis on Multiple Streams

For testing the application scalability potential when more HA resources are available, the CLUE SYCL application was run with 1, 2 and 3 concurrent HA devices to process 100 events each time. By measuring how much time it took to process the events, the throughput value is obtained and plotted in Fig 8.

Figure 8: Performance curves for running with 1, 2 and 3 streams

From the graph it can be observed that using 2 streams, in other words, 2 concurrent devices, gives twice the performance of using 1 device, especially as the input size gets larger. When the input size is smaller, it's possible that the framework overhead is a more important factor than the algorithm execution.

When using 3 streams an unexpected behavior occurred: for large input sizes, the performance is slightly improved in comparison with 2 streams, but for small input sizes the performance is worse. One possible explanation is that the synchronization functions described in Section 4.1 are causing a locking problem or are suspending the execution of the event scheduling thread. Another possible cause is that GPUs were being used by other users while conducting the benchmarking of the application and this altered the results.

6 Conclusions

During this work, the SYCL programming model was investigated and applied to make a heterogeneous implementation of the CLUE clustering algorithm. The algorithm proved to be capable of running on Intel and NVIDIA devices with performance near the original native implementation. It was even enhanced with the capacity of running on multiple device streams to perform multiple event processing jobs concurrently. This resulted in an open source powerful

heterogeneous clustering algorithm with applications in HEP but many other clustering problems. To allow compilation targeting NVIDIA GPUs, it was necessary to build the open-source Intel DPC++ LLVM compiler and install it, along with additional low-level runtimes in CERN virtual machines. During this project, the learned knowledge was written down in guides for facilitating the development of future SYCL projects.

6.1 SYCL Impressions

SYCL is a cross-platform performance porting technology that has developed to a point of providing an easy-to-learn API to write applications that perform very well on hardware accelerators. Its close similarity to OpenCL or CUDA makes it very intuitive and easy to port an existing application into SYCL. However, as a new technology, it still has a lot of improvement areas in documentation and learning resources on the internet.

6.2 Future Work

The progress and attention received by SYCL from the heterogeneous computing community have increased in recent years. Many research papers have been published with interesting findings that could be useful for the CLUE application. Also, SYCL has an asynchronous synchronization mechanism by using event dependencies and kernel launching requirements. Using these features it could be possible to make a code synchronization module for the pixel track framework to improve the execution throughput when running with multiple streams.

7 References

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8 Appendix A

8.1 ClusterIndex testing algorithm

```
def areClusterIndexCorrect(outputPoints, referencePoints, n):
    areEqual = true
    clusterIdsMap = {}
    # Build points to reference clusterIndex map
    for i in range(n):
        currPoint = outputPoints[i]
        refPoint = referencePoints[i]
        if currPoint.clusterIndex == -1
            continue
        if currPoint.isSeed:
            clusterIdsMap[currPoint.clusterId] = refPoint.clusterId
    # Check for equality using the map to translate into correct clusterIndex
    for i in range(n):
        currPoint = outputPoints[i]
        refPoint = referencePoints[i]
        if clusterIdsMap[currPoint.clusterId] != refPoint.clusterId:
            areEqual = false
            break
    return areEqual
```

Listing 2: ClusterIndex validation algorithm written in python for better code linting

8.2 CLUE module design for Pixeltrack Framework

Figure 9: CLUE modules integrated into Pixeltrack Framework: (A) the algorithm clusterizer, (B) the output writer and (C) the results validator.

